

RESILIENCE OF ROMANIAN ENERGY SYSTEM IN THE CONTEXT OF RUSSIAN – EUROPEAN UNION TENSIONS

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Abstract: *This article realizes an analysis of economic and energy relations between Russia and the European countries, focusing on the Romanian energy system resilience against the risks of interruption of imported gas supply. As is known, the Romanian energy system provides, at internally level, industrial and population consumption, and an effective crisis, not only imminent, on Russian gas disruption would generate a major economic and social disruption in Romania. In the context of scenario plausibility of the regional energy crisis, the components of a resilient energy system in Romania are analyzed both from a comparative perspective with other countries in the European Union (EU) and experts from the Romanian institutions. This analysis is needed to draw conclusions for the authorities and civil society. Paper is analyzing the economic and geostrategic Romanian-Russian and EU-Russia relations. The model of gas crisis of 2006 and 2009 between Russia and Ukraine, with visible effects on Germany, could be analyzed using possible important pillars of the new crisis. By using the approach developed in this paper we point the energy trade with Russia and Romania's dependence on Russian gas. Another important coordinate of the paper is to prevent social and economic impacts of energy resources imported from Russia. In this sense, the paper is done knowing the vulnerabilities and the strengths of the institutions and of the companies that provide energy in Romania. This approach is an element of economic and social stability, so that the energy system resilience is interdependent with the resilience of the population at the risks generated by the threats of an energy crisis (natural gas). Russian-Ukrainian population must be prepared for such a scenario by trying to mitigate the possible consequences if the crisis materializes.*

Key-Words: *Romanian energy system resilience, Russian-European Union threat crisis, regional energy crisis, vulnerabilities and strengths of the institutions and of the companies*

1. Introduction

In the context of globalization, Romanian development and economic independence represent important challenges. Efforts and actions of all those involved in Romania's economic sustainability must converge towards the same goal, namely the promoting the national interest in collective consciousness. In the current context of the crisis in our region or its related geopolitical implications, Romanian state should support measures that lead to appropriate responses for energy security system. In this direction the Ministry of Foreign Affairs enroll their actions, especially through General Department for Economic Diplomacy which was created for twinning different business environments within and abroad Romania. In terms of energy system resiliency, economic diplomacy's main components are supporting and promoting energy security objectives. In order to succeed in achieving the objectives mentioned above must [1]:

- support the European Union objectives and projects aiming at achieving energy security and developing a stable economic environment, with special emphasis on climate change mitigation;
- promote the European Energy Strategy objectives with regard to security of supply, higher internal market competitiveness and support for sustainable energy;
- involve actively in the accomplishment of major energy projects and in supporting additional proposals.

“The direction of causality between electricity consumption and economic growth has four estimable hypotheses (Tiwari, 2010, 2011). The first hypothesis reveals the importance of electricity consumption for economic growth directly or indirectly through use of capital and labor in economic activity where labor and capital are considered as complements. If an increase in economic growth is linked with an increase in electricity consumption, the causal relation is running from electricity consumption to economic growth. In such an environment, energy (electricity) conservation policies may be harmful for economic growth. On the contrary, if there is unidirectional causality from economic growth to electricity consumption then conservation hypothesis postulates that electricity consumption is determined by economic growth. In such case, electricity conservation policies do not have adverse effect on economic growth. Thirdly, the interdependent relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth is considered as feedback hypothesis. The feedback hypothesis can be highlighted by the existence of bidirectional causal relation between electricity consumption and economic growth. This hypothesis concludes that electricity conservation policies may retard economic growth by reduction in electricity consumption in an economy and fluctuations in economic growth furthermore reduce demand for electricity due to feedback effect from economic growth to electricity consumption. Finally, neutrality hypothesis suggests that there is a minor role of electricity consumption in economic growth which is validated when there is no causality between both the variables. This implies that reduction in electricity use through electricity (energy) conservation policy will have no adverse effect on economic growth.” (Mutașcu et al., 2011)

2 Method and data for Romanian Energy System in the context of Russian – European Union Threats Crisis

(a) **Method** used for this paper is modeling data and, for the future, trying to calibrate the model. In order to calibrate the data and the method of the paper, we used Markal model, which optimizes the total energy system cost. In *Deterministic Markal Elastic Demand*, William Usher assumed that this approach is possible through smart investment choosing and operation of all interconnected network elements. The participants of this network are assumed to have perfect inter-temporal knowledge of future policy and economic developments. Hence, under a range of input assumptions, which are essential to the model outputs, Markal delivers an economy-wide solution of cost-optimal energy market development. Substantial efforts have been made in respect of the transparency and completeness of the model structure and assumptions, including through a range of stakeholder events [for example, expert peer review, and publication of the model documentation [6],[4],[9]. According to Usher, each demand has constant own-price elasticity (E) in a given period. In this case, the demand function correlated to energy is expression of demand for some energy service (ES), demand in the reference case (ES_0), marginal price of each energy service demand (p), marginal price of each energy service demand in the reference case (p_0) and exponent of own-price elasticity of the demand (E), as follows:

$$\frac{ES}{ES_0} = \left(\frac{p}{p_0}\right)^E$$

Besides the mentioned factors, specific to the resilience of the energy system the model was developed by Skea et al. [3], introducing new indicators, namely:

- **for primary energy supply**: import dependence, largest single source of supply, diversity/concentration of energy supply, energy portfolios (see table 1);

Table 1. Possible resilience indicators for primary energy supply

Indicator	Type of Event	Type of Incertitude	Notes
Import dependence	Supply interruption	Uncertainty Ignorance	Could be for the whole economy or specific sectors.
Largest single source of Supply	Supply interruption	Uncertainty Ignorance	Could be for the whole economy or specific sectors.
Diversity/concentration of energy supply (e.g. Herfindahl-Hirschman Index)	Supply interruption Price shocks	Uncertainty Ignorance	HHI is used by the Office of Fair Trading to assess market concentration.
Energy Portfolios	Price volatility	Risk	Energy mixes which are efficient in terms of volatility/cost along a frontier have been explored by Awerbuch and Roques using financial portfolio theory. Could be for the whole economy or for specific sectors.

Source: Jim Skea, Modassar Chaudry, Paul Ekins, Kannan Ramachandran, Anser Shakoor, Xinxin Wang, *A resilient energy system*, in Paul Ekins, Jim Skea, Mark Winskel, *Energy 2050: Making the Transition to a Secure Low-Carbon Energy System*, Taylor and Francis, 2011, pp.151

- **for energy infrastructure**: statistical probability of supply interruption in network industries (gas and electricity), expected number of annual hours in which energy is

undistributed, value and/or level of undistributed energy, energy storage capacity and/or stocks by fuel and market, redundancy in network architecture (see table 2);

Table 2. Possible resilience indicators for energy infrastructure

Indicator	Type of Event	Type of Incertitude	Notes
Statistical probability of supply interruption in network industries (gas and electricity)	Technical equipment failure Weather-related risks Inadequacy of investment	Risk	Specify as a security standard (i.e. a probability) to allow for the greater use of intermittent supply sources driving up capacity margins
Expected number of annual hours in which energy is unserved	As above	Risk	
Value/level of Energy	As above	Risk	
Energy storage capacity and/or stocks by fuel and market	Interruption of supply	Uncertainty	Could be measured in hours/days/weeks
Largest single source of supply in a market energy	Interruption of supply	Uncertainty	Expressed as a percentage of supply in any given market
Redundancy in network Architecture	Attack on infrastructure	Ignorance	The number of pinch points/critical nodes which would need to go down to cause interruption of supply to consumers. The networks could include gas, electricity and distribution of refined oil products

Source: Jim Skea, Modassar Chaudry, Paul Ekins, Kannan Ramachandran, Anser Shakoor, Xinxin Wang, *A resilient energy system*, in Paul Ekins, Jim Skea, Mark Winskel, *Energy 2050: Making the Transition to a Secure Low-Carbon Energy System*, Taylor and Francis, 2011, pp.151

- *for energy users*: energy demand level, energy intensity, energy costs, back-up arrangements for energy sensitive users (see table 3);

Table 3. Possible resilience indicators for energy users

Indicator	Type of Event	Type of Incertitude	Notes
Energy demand level	Supply interruption Price shocks	Risk Uncertainty	Often taken as proxy for exposure to supply interruptions and price shocks in policy formulation. This could be applied to specific sectors e.g. residential housing, critical transport or types of business
Energy intensity	Supply Interruption	Uncertainty	kWh/£ for industry (output) and economy as a whole (GDP). kWh per household in the domestic sector. This indicator should represent the capacity for some degree of energy service needs to be met in the event of supply interruption.
Energy costs	Price volatility Price shocks	Risk Uncertainty	% energy expenditure as proportion of output, expenditure and GDP for industry, households and economy as a whole respectively. This indicator points to the broader economic impact of price shocks.
Back-up arrangements for energy sensitive users, e.g. hospitals, banks	Supply interruption	Uncertainty	

Source: Jim Skea, Modassar Chaudry, Paul Ekins, Kannan Ramachandran, Anser Shakoor, Xinxin Wang, *A resilient energy system*, in Paul Ekins, Jim Skea, Mark Winskel, *Energy 2050: Making the Transition to a Secure Low-Carbon Energy System*, Taylor and Francis, 2011, pp.152

- *for energy macro-level*: final energy demand, primary energy supply, electricity generation mix (see table 4);

Table 4. Macro-level resilience indicators

Indicator	Quantified assumption
Final energy demand	Final energy demand falls 3.2% pa relative to GDP from 2010 onwards.
Primary energy supply	No single energy source (e.g. gas) accounts for more than 40% of the primary energy mix from 2015 onwards
Electricity generation mix	No single type of electricity generation (e.g. gas, nuclear) accounts for more than 40% of the mix from 2015 onwards

Source: Jim Skea, Modassar Chaudry, Paul Ekins, Kannan Ramachandran, Anser Shakoor, Xinxin Wang, A resilient energy system, in Paul Ekins, Jim Skea, Mark Winskel, Energy 2050: Making the Transition to a Secure Low-Carbon Energy System, Taylor and Francis, 2011, pp.153

(b) Data

Our following approach is connected to Romanian gas system data. According to Annual Reports for Monitoring Internal Market of Natural Gas (2012, 2013) we adapted and modelled data. Hereby, import dependence decreased from 24,32% in 2012 to 15,28% in 2013 (fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Import, natural gas for 2011/2012/2013

Source: Autoritatea Națională de Reglementare în Domeniul Energiei, *Raport intern de monitorizare pentru piața internă de gaze naturale*, 2013

Regarding to Herfindahl - Hirschman Index, measuring diversity/concentration of energy supply in enterprises competition), in Romania were constant from 2012 to 2013, meaning that equilibrium is maintained.

Fig. 2 Diversity/concentration of energy supply (Herfindahl Hirschman Index)

2012

2013

Source: Autoritatea Națională de Reglementare în Domeniul Energiei, Raport intern de monitorizare pentru piața internă de gaze naturale, 2013

Diversity of energy supply, import and gas consumption influence the evolution of natural gas price from 2012 to 2013 in the sense of decreasing.

Fig. 3 Monthly evolution of natural gas price from import (lei/MWh)

Source: Autoritatea Națională de Reglementare în Domeniul Energiei, Raport intern de monitorizare pentru piața internă de gaze naturale, 2012 and 2013

From the data we conclude that in Romania the consumption of gas has declined in the last years, but the deposits have grown-up because of the Russian crisis risk. All this remind us that the premises of risk resilience, in energy system, are potential in Romania, not because of the real lack of gas, but of the psychological terror exercised by Russia in the conflict with European Union and indirectly with Romania.

3. The elements of the resilience of Romanian Energy System in the context of Russian Federation' threat with natural gas interruption

Most geopolitical and geo-strategic analyses of the Russian-Ukrainian and Russian Federation - European Union conflicts lead to a generally accepted idea, that, given the significant dependence of European countries on Russian natural gas, Russian Federation uses the provision of commercial relationship as a means of coercion in international relations, with a major impact, particularly on neighboring states.

In addition to Ukraine, whose strained relations with the Russian Federation have escalated to the annexation of territories and military conflicts, Romania is subject, in turn, of threats and even coercive measures in trade with the Russian Federation, having as mobile the gas supply interruption. In this regard, besides almost constant messages of Russian officials,

repeated proposals to increase the price of gas, the attempt to put pressure on the Romanian state, through the energy system, has been realized by the recent reduction in gas supply dated October 8, 2014 announced by Gazprom Transgaz as 18% compared to the quantities nominated on the basis of Romanian beneficiaries' needs.

In front of these threats and disruptive measures, Romanian authorities have the responsibility of strengthening the resilience of the energy system, this option being widely appreciated by the experts in the field, as the main way to prevent and counteract the consequences of the gas crisis.

The resilience of the energy system in Romania is defined as its ability to prepare for and cope with threats and possible disruption of gas supply, so household consumption and economic operators being provided, under normal conditions, as such disturbance would not be occurred. Resilience expresses the extent to which energy system in Romania, for the component of natural gas, can cope and, especially, can overcome any crisis situation, back to working condition after a significant impairment of the users.

To strengthen the resilience of the energy system to the gas crisis experienced by some European countries in 2009, the literature mentions a number of measures [2], such as:

- *energy mix and the diversification of its sources of imports;*
- *drawing on domestic supply stockholdings and on energy solidarity mechanisms with allied countries for rapid, short-term supply substitutions;*
- *ability to substitute fuels at short notice in industry and power generation;*
- *ability to enforce some degree of rationing on domestic demand;*
- *ability to operate parts of the infrastructure in reverse flow.*

All these measures, mainly preventive, define resilience of the energy system in its classical form/meaning, oriented to technical capabilities, in order to achieve its basic objective, to ensure an optimal level of natural gas for the consumers/customers, given the interruption of imports from the Russian Federation.

From this perspective, Romanian energy system seems to be able to cope with a natural gas crisis, even if the Russian Federation would interrupt all power, as shown in the official position of the Department of Energy from the day when the supply was reduced by 18%. Thus, it is stated that "people will not be affected in any way by these cuts, even if the Russians cease all deliveries until spring" as "national production reached 31 million cubic meters per day, while the consumption is about 16 million cubic meters per day. In addition, the deposits are more than 2.4 billion cubic meters to 1.7 billion cubic meters, as was necessary storage for this winter. "These official assurances reflect major developments in the energy market, as well as the preventive measures taken by Romania, to strengthen the resilience of the energy system to the gas crisis in the Russian Federation.

However, the resilience of the energy system is beyond all technical measures for ensuring optimum gas to beneficiaries, a policy or strategy of defense against threats of all economic and social components dependent of energy system, induced by threats or constraints of the Russian Federation on EU countries using commercial relationship in gas supply. As mentioned Edward Hunter Christie, an economist at the Vienna Institute for International Economic Studies, "target function of the supplier is increasingly well

understood within European policy circles that the Russian Federation seeks to control foreign policy orientation of the countries in its “near abroad”.

According to recent sociological research, 27% of the population believes that the risk of starting a conflict between Romania and Russia is “very high” and “high” and Romania's energy security is perceived as “pretty poor” - 37% and “very poor” - 12%. Behold, if at the technical level, the Department of Energy provides assurance that any Russian gas crisis would not affect the consumers in Romania, at the social level, the perception of threats to energy security is problematic, which may cause important socio-economic interference. Thus, there is defined a particular model for resilience of Romania energy system against the threat of interruption of gas imports from the Russian Federation, who directs both to the technical and to the social, political and economic elements.

In this regard, in addition to indicators Markal model, it must assess the energy security threat perception, embodied in indicators such as:

- *attempt to destabilize the country's economy;*
- *the modality to negotiate higher prices for imported natural gas from the Russian Federation;*
- *strategies of psychological warfare, aimed at creating panic among the people and responsible institutions;*
- *political elements, whereby are tracked geo-strategic/geopolitical advantages;*
- *preventing the exploitation of alternative resources (shale gas, LPG);*
- *maintaining and conservation of the Russian status as leading regional and European actor in supplying natural gas.*

At the same time, it aims to implement effective solutions adapted to the national context, covering the following:

- *supporting the building of gas pipeline for alternative transportation, like South Stream;*
- *increasing quantities of natural gas storage;*
- *use of natural resources storage that Romania currently has;*
- *effective public communication strategy for informing the public in a fair and transparent mode;*
- *growing consumer confidence, so as not to put pressure on the supplier or competent institutions;*
- *prompt and efficient cooperation with the media;*
- *exploitation of unconventional resources (shale gas, LPG) to help avoid malfunctions.*

Based on these indicators, we designed a model for analyzing the resilience of the energy system in Romania in relation to gas supply disruption threats from the Russian Federation, to be validated, after significant quantitative and qualitative data collection from recognized Romanian experts in oil and gas industry.

The research method chosen is based on a questionnaire survey, at this stage of the study being prepared and subjected to pre-testing the research instrument. The group of respondents to the pre-testing phase questionnaire consisted of eight top specialists, including:

- three top management officials of oil and gas companies active in Romania, with over 30 years' experience in the industry;
- three experts from the middle management of oil and gas companies active in Romania, with a solid knowledge of the regional gas market;
- two independent experts with an academic career in the energy field and a good knowledge of Romanian industry.

Even if in statistical terms, according to a group of experts, relatively small, the data recorded impose limits in the generalization of the results and the conclusions, the relevance of the feedback from the experts with experience in top positions in gas industry, determine us, that, besides adjusting the research tool, to analyze also the replies, to outline a first image on the elements and the particularities of the resilience of energy system in Romania, for natural gas component. Thus, following tabulation of results from the 8 expert questionnaires revealed the following **relevant issues**:

1. In accordance with ideas expressed by the interviewed experts, the energy system in Romania, for natural gas component, is resilient against a possible gas crisis in the Russian Federation.

2. There were identified main technical, organizational or managerial characteristics of energy system in Romania, which help to strengthen its resilience, as shown in the table below.

Table 4. Summary of responses of experts on measures to strengthen the resilience of the energy system in Romania for natural gas component

Summary of responses of experts on measures to strengthen the resilience of the energy system in Romania for natural gas component
<p><i>a. Develop storage capacity by increasing storage capacity in the hot season, at lower prices.</i></p> <p><i>b. Develop regional interconnection solutions and upgrading their networks to parameters that allow interconnection.</i></p> <p><i>c. Improve balanced energy mix by increasing the share of nuclear energy.</i></p> <p><i>d. Accelerating the implementation of the concept of intelligent networks (Smart Grids) to bring more information to decision points.</i></p> <p><i>e. Reorganization of transmission and distribution activities, also of local dispatches, in symmetrical structures on the 8 regions of the country, in order to minimize risks and optimize costs.</i></p> <p><i>f. Reorientation of the domestic consumption of natural gas to alternatives with higher returns (electric energy or high efficiency cogeneration, biogas, biomass, etc.).</i></p> <p><i>g. The construction of compressed natural gas terminals, and liquefied petroleum gas in seaports and Romanian Danube.</i></p> <p><i>h. Continued private investment in the exploitation of hydrocarbons, which brought Romania into the current situation of energy independence.</i></p> <p><i>i. Increase competence.</i></p> <p><i>j. Encourage individual energy solutions by informative programs (on site generation, micro storage etc).</i></p>

Source: Authors

3. In case of gas supply interruption to domestic and industrial consumers, even if this might not occur as a result of cessation, even total, of imports from the Russian Federation,

such a crisis would create some economic and social destabilizing consequences, as identified by experts and presented in the table below.

Table 5. Summary of experts' responses on the of destabilizing consequences in case of a gas crisis in Romania

Summary of experts' responses on the of destabilizing consequences in case of a gas crisis in Romania
<p>a. <i>Loss of competitiveness in the industry leads to economic impact and unemployment, with social effects.</i></p> <p>b. <i>The population, through media, would put an immense pressure on politicians to adopt any solution, even at the risk of long-term strategies diversion.</i></p> <p>c. <i>Some politicians would use the moment to promote their own interests in the field.</i></p> <p>d. <i>The companies, through lobbying and communication, would inflame public space, without an immediate tangible impact.</i></p>

Source: Authors

4. The most important preventive measure, which in the interviewed experts' opinion should be adopted in Romania for a good management of a gas crisis in the Russian Federation, implicitly maintaining resilient energy system is an effective public communication strategy for informing the public in a fair and transparent mode.

5. The threat of Russian Federation concerning the interruption of supplying natural gas to Romania primarily represents political elements, whereby it has tracked geo-strategic and geo-political advantages, and the desire to maintain and preserve Russia' status as a leading regional and European actor in supplying natural gas.

4. Conclusions

The distribution and transport of natural gas in Romania would not create disruptions to household and industrial power, when ceasing, even total natural gas imported from the Russian Federation. It has the technical capability, storage and transportation necessary to ensure normal consumption whether such gas crisis would occur in cold weather. The resilience of the energy system in Romania is more an enhanced technical and organizational component, and is relatively vulnerable to population pressure, media and policy makers which are able to divert even long-term strategies adopted in the gas industry.

The threat of the Russian gas crisis tends to acquire the characteristics of a war/conflict mainly psychologically oriented on much larger segments of population than those that could be actually affected by an interruption of imports. This requires a reconsideration of the resilience of the energy system in Romania, targeting also the interferences of the interdependent systems with the energy system.

Considering the specific energy system in Romania, the prospects for its development, and the ability to exploit its natural gas resources, which can provide full current use, some elements of Markal model, as well as its premises to deter gas crisis in Russian Federation with regard to beneficiaries in the EU, as stated by Edward Hunter Christie (2009) are not fully applicable for Romania, which requires an adjustment and supplement of the factors that contribute to strengthening the resilience of the energy system.

Validating a specific model of energy system resilience for Romania, based on the foregoing, in addition to knowledge and monitoring vulnerabilities and strengths of the institutions that provide energy, is an element of economic and social stability by strengthening social component, interrelated with functioning energy system, but also with the perception of risks to energy security.

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